

Plant elongation ability and submergence tolerance of deepwater (floating) rice varieties of Bangladesh, BRRI, Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh, 1978.

Variety	Plant ht before flooding ^a (cm)	Plant elongation ability ^b	Elongation (cm/day)	Submergence tolerance ^c
Habiganj Aman 1	113	81	9	5
Habiganj Aman 2	98	119	12	5
Habiganj Aman 3	92	134	12	6
Habiganj Aman 4	98	104	10	6
Habiganj Aman 5	91	121	11	6
Habiganj Aman 6	92	129	12	7
Habiganj Aman 7	103	119	12	6
Habiganj Aman 8	90	122	11	8
Rayada 15-01	88	99	9	6
Rayada 16-02	86	96	8	7
Rayada 16-04	64	141	9	6
Rayada 16-10	67	135	9	8
Lal Aman 6 34	83	104	9	8
Lal Aman 594	100	97	10	6
Lal Aman 127	95	96	9	8
Lal Aman 648	86	105	9	8
Kala Aman 735/1	74	129	10	9
Matia Aman 738/1	94	89	8	8
Matia Aman 5 75	96	110	10	8
Gowai 576	96	107	10	8
Haloi	87	28	2	7

^a Ht measured at 45 days after sowing.

^b Measured in percentage of height increase over basal height after 10 days of flooding.

^c Rated according to Standard Evaluation System for rice of IRTP 5 days after submergence.

Mean and range of elongation (cm/day) of floating rice varieties during 10 days of flooding, Joydebpur, Dacca.

3 days, elongation was fairly stable (10–11 cm/day), but on the 4th day, it suddenly rose to as high as 20 cm/day,

then dropped on the 5th to 7th days. On the 8th and 9th days, elongation rate rose slightly before it again stabilized.

The mechanism of deepwater effect on rice

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Some plants of the variety Krasnodarsky 424 were submerged in water for 72 hours at the 2-leaf stage while the control plants were not submerged. Every 24 hours the contents of ribonucleic acid (RNA) and deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA), the RNA:DNA ratio, the content of histones, and the ribonuclease (RNase) activity were determined in the plant apices.

The RNA: DNA ratio of submerged plants decreased (Fig. 1). Simultaneously

1. The dynamics of DNA: RNA ratio in apices of unsubmerged and submerged plants. Krasnodar, Kalinina, USSR.

2. The dynamics of ribonuclease (RNase) activity in apices of unsubmerged and submerged plants. Krasnodar, Kalinina, USSR.

3. The dynamics of histone contents in apices of unsubmerged and submerged plants. Krasnodar, Kalinina, USSR.

there was a sharp increase in RNase activity (Fig. 2) and RNA destruction. The results also indicated a blocking of new DNA regions with histones (Fig. 3), which also caused the DNA functional activity (RNA:DNA) to decrease.

The yield of the experimental plants was greater than that of the control because productive tillering increased in the experimental plants. The difference in silicon dioxide content in the straw of experimental and control plants was not statistically significant.

tillers, nonetheless disease-free externally, are also observed in the same infected hill. Ratoons growing from infected hills develop typical symptoms of udbatta, indicating the systemic nature of the disease. Ratoons appear to be an efficient mechanism of disease persistence in the off-season and possibly in the subsequent crop.

Of 400 rice varieties in experimental plots and seed multiplication areas at Rokupr in 1977, 25 were infected: BD2, L78, Morobekkan, ROK 1,2526, 7446, 563, Faro 14, Gissi 25, IR5, AA8A, Thoo 2, BG32-2, RH2, Pa Panell, CJ5-2, Murungakayan 304 B, Murungakayan, Anethoda, ROK 4, ROK 3, AUS 61, SR 26, Nachin 11, and ROK 7. The level of infection found indicated varietal differences, but earlier reports indicate that disease incidence varies considerably from season to season. Therefore, it is unsafe to draw conclusions based on 1 year's results.

Preliminary disease surveys in the 1977 cropping season in the mangrove swamps along the Scarcies Rivers estuary in Sierra Leone established udbatta as a potential major disorder of rice inflorescence in this ecology. The disease incidence was recorded using the following procedure. In each site, farmers' fields along the rivers and creeks were

Pest management and control DISEASES

Incidence of udbatta in the mangrove swamps of northern Sierra Leone

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The occurrence of the cattail fungus, sugary disease or udbatta disease, on rice in the mangrove swamps of northern Sierra Leone was first reported by Deighton in 1946. The disease, however, had been observed much earlier on wild graminaceous alternate hosts, including *Oryza brachyantha*. The disease appears identical to that reported from India and other Asian countries but the causative organism in Sierra Leone is *Ephelis pallida*. *E. pallida* has smaller spores than *Ephelis oryzae*, the Indian organism. Little is known about its biology and mode of infection.

Disease symptoms appear after flowering when the inflorescence emerges as a small, cylindrical rod with spikelets matted together by mycelium. The infected spikelet exudes small, black fruiting bodies, and no grain formation takes place. When the disease develops later, only a few spikelets may show mycelium and fruiting body development;

the remaining spikelets are usually sterile. The yield of an affected panicle is practically nil, therefore the percentage of infection can roughly be translated as that percentage in yield reduction.

Sometimes the panicle bases are spirally twisted, and the flag leaf is invariably covered with a fine layer of white mycelium that spreads to the base of the leaf and into the culm. The flag leaf is greatly reduced in some varieties, but not in others. A few unproductive

Incidence of udbatta disease and its effect on panicle development in farmers' fields in the Scarcies Rivers estuary, Sierra Leone, October 1977 to January 1978.

Location/ variety	Samples (no.)	Hills (no./sample)	Diseased hills (no./sample)	Disease incidence (%)	Diseased panicles per infected hill (%)	Panicles affected (%)
Kasiri/ Local, unknown	15	9.7±0.9	1.5± 0.9	18.6±6.4 (8.3–66.7) ^a	9.2± 4.3 (4.3–18.8) ^a	0.7
Rokupr/ Local, unknown	11	18.4±3.3	1.5± 0.7	8.6± 4.7 (5.0–17.0)	9.6± 4.8 (4.0–20.0)	0.8
Tumbu Walla/ Pa Dohnut	13	12.8±2.5	1.6± 0.7	12.9±10.1 (6.3–22.2)	17.4±12.1 (4.8–50.0)	1.1
Mambolo/ Pa Compan	10	10.5±2.2	1.8± 1.3	17.8±13.2 (6.7–50.0)	13.7±7.3 (4.3–27.8)	1.3
Balansera/ Pa Merr	3	23.0±2.7	4.0± 1.0	18.0±6.2 (13.0–25.0)	19.2±10.3 (11.8–31.0)	6.3
Mapotonon/ Pa Taylor	3	30.3±4.9	15.7± 11.7	49.0±33.2 (11.0–72.0)	23.7±19.9 (8.0–46.0)	7.6

^aFigures in parentheses give range of incidence.